

Investigation of virulence factors in enterococci isolated from clinical samples

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Abstract

Introduction: *Enterococcus* species are opportunistic pathogens that are common in the gut microbiota of both humans and animals. They can withstand a variety of challenging conditions. Interestingly, cytolysin A (*cylA*), serine proteases *E* (*sprE*), hyaluronidase (*hyl*), and pathogenicity islands (PAIs) are among the virulence factors that enterococci carry. The purpose of this study is to determine whether clinically isolated enterococci samples contain these virulence factors.

Material and method: In order to identify one hundred enterococci isolates that were taken from clinical specimens at the Qom Laboratory in 1399, biochemical confirmation tests were performed. In order to identify the presence of four virulence genes (PAIs, *cylA*, *sprE*, and *hyl*), specific primers for uniplex-PCR were created.

Results: Out of the 100 clinical specimens, *E. faecalis* was detected in 55 (55%) cases, *E. faecium* in 10 (10%) cases, and other *Enterococcus* species in 35 (35%) cases. The isolates exhibited a virulence gene predominance of 40%, 34%, 6%, and 45% for PAI, *cylA*, *sprE*, and *hyl*, respectively.

Discussion and conclusion: In contrast to *E. faecium* or other *Enterococcus* species, our study highlights a noticeably higher prevalence of virulence gene carriage within the *E. faecalis* group. PCR is notable for its higher specificity when compared to phenotypic techniques.

Keywords: Enterococcus, virulence factors, Polymerase Chain Reaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Enterococcus species are catalase-negative, gram-positive bacteria that are usually found in short chains or pairs. Enterococci are well known for their adherence; they can grow in unfavourable circumstances with 6.5% table salt and 40% bile salts, for example. They can withstand temperatures between 10 and 40 degrees Celsius as well as a pH of 6.9, which allows for long-term growth in these conditions. Enterococci are opportunistic pathogens that are common in the digestive tracts of many different animals and insects. They are essential components of the human intestinal microbiota. The oral cavity, genitalia, and skin, especially the perineal area, are additional sites of colonization [1,2].

McCallum and Hastings were the first to notice the pathogenic potential of enterococci in the late 1800s. *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* stand out as the most common pathogens in humans among the twelve pathogenic enterococci species that have been found [3]. According to research, *Enterococcus faecalis* is responsible for 80% to 90% of human enterococcal infections, with *Enterococcus faecium* responsible for the remaining 5–15% of cases. Urinary tract infections, wound infections, and endocarditis are frequent manifestations of these illnesses [4].

When their significance in hospital-acquired infections became clear, enterococci were mainly thought to be unimportant bacteria until 1970. The 1988 English case that was the first to be reported of vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* raised awareness of these bacteria. As of right now, hospital-acquired infections are primarily caused by enterococci. Generally, *Enterococcus* species are not regarded as primary pathogens; infection typically occurs in individuals with severe underlying illnesses or compromised immune systems [5,6].

The bacterium possesses unique characteristics that enable it to withstand and adapt to harsh environments, allowing it to infiltrate and destroy a wide range of bodily tissues easily. Enterococci also carry many pathogenic genes, which enable them to enter and penetrate a variety of tissues. The development of high-level resistance to aminoglycosides in enterococci compromises the effectiveness of this class of antibiotics against enterococcal infections. Finding vancomycin-resistant enterococci further complicates treatment options because vancomycin is the primary medication used to treat infections caused by this bacterium. Finally, the presence of multiple virulence genes in enterococci significantly increases intra-hospital transmission and promotes their penetrative growth. These virulence factors are pivotal in enhancing enterococci's resilience and stability in hospital

settings, thus constituting a significant driver of nosocomial infections associated with these pathogens [7,8].

Over the last twenty years, a great deal of study has been done to clarify many of the virulence factors that enterococci possess. Nevertheless, the exact processes by which these pathogenic components interact with the host and cause disease are still mostly unknown [9]. Surface adhesins, colonization factors like AS and LTA, host immune system inhibitors like AS, and bacteriocins like cytolysin and AS-48 are a few of these virulence factors. Furthermore, enterococci have pro-inflammatory factors such as sex pheromones and tissue-invading factors like LTA superoxidase, gelatinase, hyaluronidase, and cytolysins. Pathogenicity islands (PAIs), serine protease sprE, hyaluronidase hyl, and cytolysin cyla—which are essential virulence genes in enterococci—are among the virulence factors that are the subject of this study [10,13].

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study looks into 100 verified *Enterococcus* isolates that were taken from clinical labs in the province of Qom using a descriptive cross-sectional design. The isolates were quickly moved—into the

Primer	Sequences 5' → 3'
E.fec-F	ATCAAGTACAGTTAGTCTTTATTAG
E.fec-R	ACGATTCAAAGCTAACTGAATCAGT
E.fas-F	TTGAGGCAGACCAGATTGACG
E.fas-R	TATGACAGCGACTCCGATTCC

Table1. Primer sequences designed for the detection of *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium*

Enterococcus faecalis produced a 941 bp product, while *Enterococcus faecium* produced a 658 bp product. The PCR reaction was directed towards the particular *ddl* gene. The reaction conditions were as follows: 4 minutes of initial denaturation at 94 °C, 40 seconds of denaturation at 94 °C, 45 seconds of annealing at 55 °C, 40 seconds of extension at 72 °C, and 5 minutes of final extension at 72 °C.

PCR reaction for specific genes *hyl*, *cyla*, *sprE*, PAIS

Sinacolon manufactured the primers after they were designed using CLC Sequence Viewer version 8. Table 2 contains comprehensive details about primer sequences, their genomic locations, and the sizes of amplified fragments. The NCBI website's Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) service was used to confirm primer specificity.

target gene	Sequences	The size of the product	reaction temperature
PAIs	GACGCTCCCTTCTTTTGAC CCAGAGAAATTACTACCAT	387	50
sprE	AAGAAGTGGCAGATACAACCG TTGACCACCTGTTGTATCGATATC	515	51
hyl	AAGAGCTGCAGGAAATGGC GACGTCCAAGTTTCCAAAGG	268	52
cyla	AACAGGTTATGCATCAGATCTCTC GCTGCGCTTACTTCTGGAG	1044	51

Table2. Specific designed primers for the detection of virulence genes in enterococci.

research centre—keeping a temperature range of 1-4 degrees Celsius for two hours. On blood agar medium enriched with 5% sheep blood (Merck, Germany), pure colonies were obtained upon arrival. A battery of tests, such as gram staining, catalase tests, growth on Bile Esculin Agar medium (Merck, Germany), growth on 6.5% salt media, and L-pyrrolidinyl arylamidase test, were used to identify the specimen down to the genus level.

Luria-Bertani broth medium containing yeast extract and tryptone was used to extract DNA from 24-hour cultures (Merck, Germany). Centrifugation was used to gather the cell debris, and the Synaclone company's DNA extraction kit's instructions were followed for DNA extraction. Electrophoresis was used for the qualitative assessment of the extracted materials, and a nanodarp was used for the quantitative assessment.

PCR reaction

The Pasteur Institute of Iran provided the strains of *Enterococcus faecium* and *Enterococcus faecalis* that were used as positive controls in this study. *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* were the two particular primers listed in Table 1 that were used to identify *Enterococcus* samples at the species level.

Four target genes (*hyl*, *cyla*, *sprE*, and PAI) were evaluated using PCR reactions in a standard reaction volume of 25 microliters. One unit of Taq DNA polymerase enzyme, 100 nanograms of bacterial genome, 0.2 mM dNTPs, 1.5 mM magnesium, and 0.5 μM of each forward and reverse primer made up the reaction mixture.

The program used for amplification was as follows: 4 minutes of initial denaturation at 94 °C, 45 seconds of denaturation at 94 °C, 45 seconds of annealing at 51 °C, 45 seconds of extension at 72 °C, and 5 minutes of final extension at 72 °C. In addition, the procedure had both positive and negative controls. The negative control used deionized water in place of the bacterial genome.

2. MATERIAL AND METODS

Using species-specific primers that target *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* using PCR, *Enterococcus* isolates were identified at the species level. Among the isolates, *Enterococcus faecalis* was notably more common. The relative frequency of the several enterococcal species is shown in Graph 1.

Of the one hundred *Enterococcus* isolates examined, fifty-five (55%) were found to be *Enterococcus faecalis*, ten (10%) to be *Enterococcus faecium*, and thirty-five (35%) to be other *Enterococcus* species (Graph 1). The clinical specimens included 16 samples from different clinical sources, 18 wound samples, 15 blood samples, and 51 urine isolates (Graph 2). Furthermore, isolates were dispersed among various hospital departments: 46 samples came from internal medicine departments, 37 from pediatric departments, and 17 from specialized care units.

Graph1. Frequency of enterococci isolated from clinical isolates

Graph2. Abundance of bacteria in different samples

Figure1. PCR product electrophoresis of enterococci identification genes at the species level on 1.5% agarose gel. Well size marker 100 pairs, wells: clinical samples carrying *Enterococcus faecalis* bp940 gene (Figure A) and *Enterococcus faecium* carrying bp658 gene (Figure B).

Using the PCR technique, the frequency of the PAI, sprE, hyl, and cylA genes was examined. 40 of the 100 clinical isolates that were analyzed carried the PAI gene; these isolates were classified as various enterococci, 10.2% as *Enterococcus faecium*, and 82% as *Enterococcus faecalis*. In 83% of *Enterococcus faecalis* isolates, 5% of *Enterococcus faecium* isolates, and 12% of other enterococci, the sprE gene was found. On the other hand, only 4% of other enterococci and

Enterococcus faecium isolates and 96% of *Enterococcus faecalis* isolates have the cylA gene. Six percent of the 100 clinical isolates had the sprE gene, while thirty-four percent had the cytolysin cylA gene. Hyaluronidase gene testing revealed that only 45% of the clinical *Enterococcus* samples had positive results. The hyl gene was present in 80% of *Enterococcus faecalis* isolates and 20% of *Enterococcus faecium* isolates, while it was not detected in other enterococci.

D

C

Figure 1 The results of the PCR reaction for the desired genes, the electrophoresis of the PCR product of the PAIs gene (Figure C) and the sprE genes (Figure D)

Graph1. Examining the abundance of desired genes in isolated bacteria

Figure2. The results of the PCR reaction for the desired genes, the electrophoresis of the PCR product of the cylA gene (Figure E) and the hyl genes (Figure F)

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Discussion

An opportunistic category of pathogenic bacteria that are part of the human gut microbiota is called enterococci. *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* stand out as the most clinically relevant enterococcus species among the twelve that have been found.

In line with research from all across the world, including research done in Iran, our study likewise highlights the dominance of *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* over other known *Enterococcus* species. This dominance is probably due to both the potential pathogenicity of these two bacterial species as well as their ability to coexist as part of the regular flora inside the human physiological milieu.

Leila Arbabi et al. (2016), for example, found that 86% of patients at Milad Hospital in Tehran had both *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium*. The study was conducted at Iran University of Medical Sciences. In comparison, only 14% of the 149 individuals who underwent examination had illnesses linked to other enterococcal species. Comparable research was also carried out in China in 2016 by Hiang and colleagues, who examined 117 *Enterococcus* isolates and found that 82% and 18% of the isolates were *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium*, respectively. These results corroborate the presence of *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* in clinical settings and are consistent with the findings of our investigation [14,15].

Several international studies have consistently demonstrated that *Enterococcus faecalis* accounts for 80–90% of human enterococcal infections, with *Enterococcus faecium* accounting for the remaining 5–15% of cases. These results are supported by our investigation, which found that of the isolates analyzed, *Enterococcus faecalis* constituted 55% and *Enterococcus faecium* 10%. Significant differences in *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* prevalence between nations must be acknowledged, as several research with various frequency distributions has shown. Numerous factors, such as ethnic background, geographic location, dietary habits, medical procedures, and demographic traits like age and gender, might be blamed for these disparities. For instance, a study by Ahmed Ghasemi and colleagues conducted in Kashan in 2017 reported a prevalence of 83% for *Enterococcus faecalis* compared to 16% for *Enterococcus faecium* [16].

This is while in a similar study by Hossein Samadi and his colleagues in Tabriz city in 2014, the *Enterococcus faecalis* was found to be 56% prevalent, whereas 43% of the isolates were *Enterococcus faecium* [17]. Comparable differences in prevalence can be seen in nations that are close to and far from Iran. For example, *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* were found in 28% and 53% of clinical isolates, respectively, according to a 2016 study by Hiang in China [15]. In contrast, *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* were found in 75% and 24% of samples, respectively, according to a study done in Jordan that same year by Al-Ansar et al. These differences highlight the variation in the prevalence of *Enterococcus* species among various populations and geographical areas [18].

Our understanding of the fact that results from local studies may be region-specific and not always generalizable has been prompted by the wide range of outcomes shown in several studies carried out both in Iran and beyond. Pathogenicity islands, or PAIs, are a vital component of virulence in human pathogenic enterococci and are missing in non-virulent strains. The fact that these genomic islands contain so many additional virulence factors emphasizes how important they are. With PAIs found in 82% of *Enterococcus faecalis* isolates compared to 10% in *Enterococcus faecium*, our study's noteworthy abundance of PAIs explains why *Enterococcus faecalis* is more pathogenic than *Enterococcus faecium*. This discrepancy clarifies the differing incidence of illnesses brought on by these two species. For instance, a study conducted by Al-Tayeb et al. in India in 2015 reported a PAI frequency of 63% among 220 *Enterococcus* isolates [19].

The cytolysin *cylA* gene is one of the most prominent virulence factors linked to enterococci. This is especially noteworthy because enterococci usually show alpha hemolysis rather than hemolysis. Many commensal enterococci share the absence of the *cylA* gene, which helps explain their distinctive non-hemolytic nature. However, when it comes to enterococci linked to clinical infections, the picture changes significantly because this gene is often associated with tissue damage. The genetic composition and location of the *cylA* gene within enterococcal DNA have been thoroughly studied, and the results have shown that it interacts with pathogenicity islands (PAIs). Based on PCR detection of the *cylA* gene in 34% of isolates, we found additional gene loci related with enterococcal cytolysin beyond *cylA*. A related study in China in 2015 by Li et al. found that 8 clinical isolates out of 160 samples had a *cylA* gene frequency.

These results demonstrate the *cylA* gene's importance in enterococcal pathogenicity and point to its potential as a therapeutic target [20]. The serine protease *sprE*, which has been found in one-third of clinical enterococcal isolates, was one of the genes examined in this investigation. Remarkably, this gene was shown to be 82% prevalent in *Enterococcus faecalis*, placing it second in abundance in this species only to *cylA* (96%). Because of its enzymatic characteristics, serine protease plays a crucial role in infections that are purulent and tissue-degrading, indicating that it is involved in a variety of pathogenic processes.

In contrast to the 6% frequency found in our analysis, El Tayeb et al.'s 2015 investigation on 222 clinical *Enterococcus* isolates from three hospitals in Malaysia revealed a *sprE* gene frequency of 75%. Interestingly, the previously cited study found that 76% of *Enterococcus faecalis* had the *sprE* gene, which is in line with our results (p -value = 0.23). This concordance underscores the robustness and reliability of our findings regarding the prevalence of the *sprE* gene in *Enterococcus faecalis* isolates [21].

Encoded by the *hyl* gene, which is found at a frequency of 45% among the virulence genes investigated, is the hyaluronidase enzyme, one of the new virulence factors found in enterococci. Dissemination factors, such as hemogeluronidase enzymes, are found in many different bacteria, such as streptococci and staphylococci. These enzymes aid in tissue invasion and systemic dissemination. This tendency toward systemic dissemination is in contrast to enterococci's innate tendency toward localized infections, where systemic symptoms are less frequent. While some enterococcal strains have the potential to cause acute systemic infections, these instances are not expected. This finding is corroborated by enterococcal epidemiological research, which shows that localized infections are more common than systemic infections. For example, a 2015 study by Lee et al. in China found that the *hyl* gene frequency was just 6%, highlighting the relative rarity of this enterococci virulence factor [6].

The *hyl* gene was shown to be absent in human samples in a different study carried out in the United States by Ferguson et al. in 2016 [22]. Domestic research has also reported consistent results; Heydari et al. (2016) reported an 8% frequency of the *hyl* gene [23]. On the other hand, Nesaj et al.'s 2016 study in Hamadan revealed a frequency of 71% for the *hyl* gene, indicating a higher prevalence. However, a low *hyl* gene frequency has been identified as a recurrent feature in multiple investigations [24].

Conclusion

Over the last 20 years, a number of studies have been carried out that have revealed many enterococci virulence factors. The exact processes by which these harmful elements interact with the host and contribute to the pathophysiology of disease, however, are still mostly unknown. Pathogenicity islands (PAIs), serine protease *sprE*, hyaluronidase *hyl*, and cytolysin *cylA*, which are essential virulence genes inside enterococci, are the four main virulence factors that are the subject of this study.

Through an exploration of these virulence factors' functions and interactions, this study seeks to offer insights that could lead to more research in this area. In particular, it aims to clarify the clinical consequences of these virulence factors and how they interact with

the host, which will help us understand enterococcal pathogenesis better. In the end, this work aims to establish the foundation for future investigations focused on the complex interaction between the microbe and the host in a clinical setting.

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Conflict of Interest:

There is no conflict of interest.

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